

SELF-ASSESSMENT OF CHABAHAR FREE ZONE ORG**Mansoor Jangizehi***

* Department of Industrial Engineering, Payam_ Noor, Chabahar, Iran

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.61143**KEYWORDS:** Self-Assessment, organizational excellence model EFQM, Chabahar Free Zone ORG.**ABSTRACT**

The purpose of this study has been done based on the EFQM organizational Excellence Model to evaluate the self-assessment of performance Chabahar free zone organization. Chabahar Free Zone Organization's staff and experts made statistical population up and sample size obtained from Cochran-Orcutt formula. Data collected were used by questionnaire of organizational excellence model EFQM. In this model the maximum sum of score has been obtained 100 score (500 score enablers and 500 score result), Chabahar Free Zone Organization's obtained 47/158 score in the enabler and 53/149 on the result. Highest percentages of performance satisfaction were 93/64% relate to the result of society and the lowest percentages of performance satisfaction were 94/20 percent related to result of staffs. Most scores that have been obtained related to customer results with 35/69 and lowest score relate to results of the staff with 85/16. Regarding to this study Chabahar free zone organization has been obtained score out of 1000 as total 308 and it was evaluated average in the term of performance.

INTRODUCTION

(Vernero, U. Nabitiz, G. Bragonzi, A. Rebelli and R. Molinari, 2007). Given the importance of self-assessment in the organization we could be gain improvable areas with its strengths and weaknesses up to organizations would be able achieve desired goals with right planning, principled and systematic. Organizations in European countries used self-assessment model EFQM) many years for identified their weakness and then could provide guidelines for improvement them. But in the Iran has not been significant consideration still. EFQM is a framework of principles for the evaluation the performance of organization in the processes and results from it. Results of evaluation of this model are: weakness and improvable areas which proposed plans to reform them.(Riyahi, Behroz. (2007).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF RESEARCH METHOD

(J Davies, 2008) Organizations, in the competitive environment world today, according to limited resource for that achieved sustainable success for survival they required strategic and proper management to be able extend it to their goals. For this reason given to successful experience of the world organizations, management scientists have been created tools such as ,TQM,BS,ISO, SIX SIGMA S,PM,CRM,... 5 and if one of this tools can be used at the right time and correctly could have been good results to achieve goals and objectives of the organizations. But these tools regard to the expectations of the managers have not great satisfaction in output and with entrance of Excellence models from the 1950s and with patterning successful companies in the world they could provide a suitable framework for managing organizations in the competitive environment.

(J. Michalska, 2008). And Maine property of this model is organization's attitude (holistic) that allowed the management despite evaluation and analyzed their subordinates could compare it with other similar organizations. These models were usually designed so that provided take advantage of a variety of techniques for organizations.

EXPRESS MODEL

Self-assessment Definition

It is regular, systematic and universal review throughout the organization and help to leaderships that they could get recognition, comprehensive and inclusive about organization. (M Leticia & V. Santos, 2007).

Self-assessment benefits

1. Appropriate structure to determine strengths and areas of improvement.
2. The development of business plans and strategies improved the organization.

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3. It was brought the common language and conceptual framework for the improvement and management of the organization.

4. Related to fundamental concepts of excellence it is train the staffs and people and how they could tell their responsibilities.

Self-assessment approaches

1. Questionnaire approach
2. Workshop Approach
3. Performa Approach
4. Award Simulation Approach

Assessment models

1. Deming Model
2. Malcolm Baldrige model
3. The European EFQM model

FQM model is a systematic framework for evaluating the performance of organizations in the field of process and result of this process. Organizational excellence model EFQM is a set of methods and tools to assess the organization and also it is used as a model for excellence of organization. In this model the results of assessment are: strength and improvable areas and Strategies for improving the weaknesses. (Rhmani.Rhman, 2008).

CRITERIA AND SUB SET OF CRITERIA'S EFQM MODEL ARE:

1. Enablers: whatever the organization's ability indeed to meet its goals, including leadership, human resources, policy and strategy, partners, resources and process. It is noteworthy that the other enablers stimulated by leadership. (A. Neumann, Integrative Management systems, 2009).
2. Results: results affected by enablers and involving customer results, people results, society results and key performance results that each of them are Perception indicators (as perspective's stakeholders to the organization) and performance indicators (internal measurement). It is noteworthy that organizational excellence measurement the main results related to policy and strategy (key performance results inclusively and magnificently and then achieve them. The leader evidenced the performance of organization by planning and definition of objectives based on the processes and used empowerment and guidance and achievements and key indicators. (Riyahi, Behroz, 2007).

National Award and Excellence models have 9 standards which five criteria related to enablers and four other criteria related to results.

1. ENABLERS
 - 1-1 leadership
 - 1-2 policy & strategy
 - 1-3 people
 - 1-4 partnership & resources
 - 1-5 processes
2. RESULTS
 - 2-1 customer results
 - 2-2 people results
 - 2-3 society results
 - 2-4 key performance result

Figure 1 EFQM model

Table 1 Distribution score in the EFQM model

Criteria	leadership
leadership	100
policy	80
people	90
Partnership & resource	90
processes	140
customer results	200
people results	90
society results	60
key performance result	150
Total point	1000

The EFQM scoring system based on RADAR logic. This matrix concludes elements and attributes which listed below:

- Results.....
- Approach.....
- Deployment.....
- Assessment.....
- Review.....

Also the RADAR logic established four main components that one part relate to the evaluation of the results (R) and three others related to assessment of 'enablers' including approach (A), deployment (D) and Assessment and Refinement (A & R) and the word of (Review) has become (Refinement) in the Edition Dictionary, (Naser zadeh, Mohamad Ali, Nasrollahi, 2009).

Table 2 RADAR logic elements

Characteristics of assessment	RADAR logic elements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • related range • accuracy • Segmentation 	(Relevance & Usability)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procedures • Goals and Objectives • comparison with other organizations 	(Performance)

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> causal relationships 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fitness / rationality integration 	(Approach)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approach Implementation establishment of a systematic approach 	(Deployment)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measurement learning and creativity improvement and innovation 	(Assessment & Refinement)

Evaluation enabler's criteria

Three elements are expressed in below:

1. Approach
2. Deployment
3. Assessment & Refinement

According to the following score each of the sub-criteria to be determined:

1. Strengths
2. Improvable areas
3. Scoring System RADAR

Evaluation result's criteria

The results showed the organization what had been achieved.

Scoring related to the results achieved by the following features:

- Procedures
- Goals and Objectives
- comparison with other organizations
- causal relationships
- range

We can be easier to understand given to the brief description of the model and the scoring criteria according to the RADAR logic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Questionnaire was the modified organizational excellence's questioner. Chabahar Free Zone Organization's staff and experts made statistical population up and sample size obtained from Cochran-Orcutt formula which one of the most methods to calculate the sample size and obtained following:

$$1. \quad n = \frac{pq \frac{z^2}{d^2}}{1 + \left[\left(pq \frac{z^2}{d^2} \right) - 1 \right] \frac{1}{N}} \quad (1)$$

Where:

n=sample size. Z= the standard normal variable, which is 1.96 times the 95 percent confidence level. P= value of property in society. If you cannot give it 0 / 5 considered then variance analysis reaches its maxim level.

Q= percentage of people who are lacking in character. D= (q=1-p.) is an allowable error value.

It was should be note that the choices of experts was completely randomly.

RESEARCH FOUNDING

Results were obtained in accordance with the following table after the questionnaire is based on the EFQM model were collected and distributed.

Table 3 Table scoring

Score of section	Section	Percentage of scored	Maximum score	Scored criteria	criteria	Section
47/158	Enablers	02/34		02/34	Leadership	enablers
		25/49		04/29	policy	
		78/31		61/28	people	
		16/40		15/36	partnership &resources	
		03/29		65/30	processes	
53/149	results	67/34		35/69	Customer result	results
		94/20		85/16	People result	
		93/64		96/38	Society result	
		58/25		37/24	key performance result	
308		80/30	1000	308	Total scoring of self-assessment	

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

- Chabahar's port has been enjoyed value and great situation for most important and strategic especially in economy. Privilege of this port is communicated with international waters and Chabahar free zone organization can play important role in the development of national and regional economies. (Riyahi, Behroz, (2014).
- All though there is distance between acquisition of 30.8% of 100 percentages in the survey Response of Chabahar free zone organization, but this advantage is acceptable and appropriate for that organization that being moved towards business excellence. Evaluation of the result showed that based on the EFQM mode all nine criteria can have improvable area. Getting Performance from the result almost closed than enablers. (Razany .Abdolmhamad.2010).
- Considering that the outstanding results related to organization have been measured in the top management spread and organizational performance evaluated based on customer feedback, and also in the part of customer result can be achieve 20% of the total score, however in this study most score has been obtained from this criteria but this section 67/34 % obtained of 100% results customer. Therefore special attention to these areas can play an importance role about significant increase related to acquired privilege and excellent of Chabahar free zone.
- According to the highest scores relate to the society result , we can concluded that Perceptions of people society as an employer and a responsible member of the service including the overall picture is answering to the calls ,have been evaluated appropriately . Indeed organization measured by society and excellent organization to improve their performance used of this results.
- According to the lowest score related to peoples result, we can concluded that the organization have little attention than any other area and since human resources have important role related to the development and protect the achievements of organizations, the management should be planning and work hardy peoples have more cooperation together and made bilinear discourse between peoples (employer) and organizations and then encouraged the outstanding employers.

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